

Evaluation of the Consciousness Energy Healing Treated Berberine Chloride Using PXRD, PSA, and DSC Analysis

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Abstract

Berberine is one of the well-known traditional Chinese medicines and it has been significantly effective against various ailments. This study was performed to evaluate the effect of the Trivedi Effect®-Consciousness Energy Healing Treatment on its physicochemical properties by using PXRD, PSA, TGA/DTG, and DSC analytical techniques. The sample was divided into two parts; the first part was considered as a control sample (without treatment), while the second part was received the Consciousness Energy Healing Treatment remotely by the Biofield Energy Healer, Gopal Nayak and denoted as the treated sample. The PXRD peak intensities and crystallite sizes were altered ranging from -28.78% to 115.15% and -15.76% to 241.38%, respectively; however the average crystallite size was increased significantly by 23.05% in the treated sample compared to the control sample. The particle sizes were significantly increased by 16.89% (d₁₀), 34.41% (d₅₀), 21.88% (d₉₀), and 22.85 % {D (4,3)}, which resulted in the significant increase in the specific surface area by 14.74% in the treated sample compared to the control sample. The thermal analysis indicated 3.98% increase in weight loss and 3.64% decrease in the residue weight of the treated sample compared to the control sample. The latent heat for the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, and 6th peaks of the treated sample were significantly altered by 224.78%, 7.93%, 8.92%, -9.05%, -45.82%, and 10.93%, respectively, compared to the control sample. The overall analysis indicated that the Trivedi Effect®-Consciousness Energy Healing Treated berberine chloride might possess better solubility, absorption, and thermal stability compared to the untreated sample. Thus, the Trivedi Effect® could be used in improving the bioavailability of berberine chloride and might be used for designing the novel nutraceutical/pharmaceutical formulations to combat various diseases.

Keywords: Berberine Chloride; Consciousness Energy Healing Treatment; The Trivedi Effect®; Complementary and Alternative Medicine; Particle Size; PXRD; TGA/DTG

Introduction

Berberine is very popular and one of the well-known traditional Chinese medicines. It is significantly effective against various ailments [1]. It is an isoquinoline alkaloid with a wide variety of pharmacological importance and is reported to be found in the handful of plants widely used in botanical medical practice such as Golden seal (*Hydrastis canadensis*), Oregon grape (*Berberis aquifolium*), Barberry (*Berberis vulgaris*), and Chinese Goldthread (*Coptis chinensis*) [2]. The other important medicinal plants reported containing berberine are *Phellodendron chinense* and *Phellodendron amurense* [3]. The mechanism of action of berberine underlying on human health is through the action of the adenosine monophosphate-activated protein kinase (AMPK) [4,5]. Further, it was found that AMPK work by regulating an array of biological activities, through which the lipid, glucose, and energy imbalances can significantly normalize [6]. Among various natural supplements for maintaining the overall health, berberine is one of the effective and useful available sources that affect the body at a molecular level. The berberine products such as gel-based berberine can significantly reduce the pain, redness, oozing, and the ulcer size in people with canker sores [7]. In addition, it can be significantly used to control various pathological conditions such as polycystic ovary syndrome, congestive heart failure, liver diseases, hepatitis, gastric ulcers, diabetes, high cholesterol, high blood pressure, burns, diarrhea, glaucoma, menopausal symptoms, metabolic syndromes, obesity, osteoporosis, thrombocytopenia, trachoma, etc [8-12]. However, it was studied that berberine was poorly absorbed across the gut wall and mostly metabolized in the liver through phase I demethylation and phase II glucuronidation, after which the metabolites are excreted with the bile [13,14]. Therefore, researchers are making their effort to enhance the bioavailability of berberine and mainly focus on its physicochemical properties [15].

In this regard, the Biofield Energy Healing Treatment is one of the best studied Complementary and Alternative Medicine (CAM) that was performed and accepted worldwide. Different kinds of Energy Healing Therapies have been reported with significant clinical and non-clinical outcomes [16,17]. However, the Energy Healing Therapies have been accepted by the U.S. population and is well characterized by the National Center for Complementary and Alternative Medicine (NCCAM) [18,19]. The CAM therapies including Johrei, Reiki, therapeutic touch, yoga, Qi Gong, polarity therapy, Tai Chi, pranic healing, deep breathing, chiropractic/osteopathic manipulation, guided imagery, meditation, massage, homeopathy, hypnotherapy, progressive relaxation,

acupressure, acupuncture, special diets, relaxation techniques, Rolfing structural integration, healing touch, movement therapy, pilates, mindfulness, Ayurvedic medicine, traditional Chinese herbs and medicines in biological systems. The Trivedi Effect®-Consciousness Energy Healing therapies have been widely accepted worldwide. Consciousness Energy Healing Treatment found to be significant to improve the physicochemical properties of metals [20-22], improved crop yield [23,24] microbiology [25-27], biotechnology [28,29], improved bioavailability of many compounds [30-32], improved skin health [33,34], improved properties of nutraceuticals [35,36] cancer science research [37,38] and improved overall bone health [39-41]. This study was done to evaluate the effect of Biofield Energy Treatment on the physicochemical and thermal properties of berberine chloride in comparison to the untreated one, by using various analytical techniques.

Materials and Methods

Chemicals and Reagents

Berberine chloride was purchased from Tokyo Chemical Industry Co., Ltd., Japan. All other chemicals used during the experiments were of analytical grade available in India.

Consciousness Energy Healing Treatment Strategies

The berberine chloride sample considered for the experiment was divided into two equal parts. One part of berberine chloride sample was considered as a control sample where no Biofield Energy Treatment was provided. However, the second part of berberine chloride was received the Trivedi Effect®-Consciousness Energy Healing Treatment remotely under standard laboratory conditions for 3 minutes and known as the Biofield Energy Treated berberine chloride sample. This Biofield Energy Treatment was provided through the healer's unique energy transmission process by the renowned Biofield Energy Healer, Gopal Nayak, USA, to the test sample. Further, the control sample was treated with a "sham" healer for comparison purpose. The "sham" healer did not have any knowledge about the Trivedi Effect®-Consciousness Energy Healing Treatment. After that, the Biofield Energy Treated and untreated samples were kept in sealed conditions and characterized using PXRD, PSA, TGA/DTG, and DSC techniques.

Characterization

Powder X-ray Diffraction (PXRD) Analysis: The PXRD analysis of the control and Biofield Energy Treated

berberine chloride was performed with the help of Rigaku Mini Flex-II Desktop X-ray diffractometer (Japan) [42,43]. The Cu K α radiation source tube output voltage used was 30 kV and tube output current was 15 mA. Scans were performed at room temperature. The average size of individual crystallites were calculated from XRD data using the Scherrer's formula 1:

$$G = k\lambda/\beta\cos\theta \quad (1)$$

Where k is the equipment constant (0.94), G is the crystallite size in nm, λ is the radiation wavelength (0.154056 nm for K α 1 emission), β is the full-width at half maximum (FWHM), and θ is the Bragg angle [44].

The % change in crystallite size (G) of Berberine chloride was calculated using the following equation 2:

$$\% \text{ change in crystallite size} = \frac{[G_{\text{Treated}} - G_{\text{Control}}]}{G_{\text{Control}}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where G_{Control} and G_{Treated} are the crystallite size of the control and Biofield Energy Treated samples, respectively.

Particle Size Analysis (PSA): The particle size analysis of berberine chloride samples were conducted on Malvern Mastersizer 2000, from the UK with a detection range between 0.01 μm to 3000 μm using wet method [45]. The percent change in particle size (d) for at below 10% level (d_{10}), 50% level (d_{50}), 90% level (d_{90}), and D(4,3) was calculated using the following equation 3:

$$\% \text{ change in particle size} = \frac{[d_{\text{Treated}} - d_{\text{Control}}]}{d_{\text{Control}}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Where d_{Control} and d_{Treated} are the particle size (μm) for at below 10% level (d_{10}), 50% level (d_{50}), and 90% level (d_{90}) of the control and Biofield Energy Treated berberine chloride samples, respectively.

The % change in surface area (S) was calculated using the following equation 4:

$$\% \text{ change in surface area} = \frac{[S_{\text{Treated}} - S_{\text{Control}}]}{S_{\text{Control}}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

Where S_{Control} and S_{Treated} are the surface area of the control and Biofield Energy Treated berberine chloride samples, respectively.

Thermal Gravimetric Analysis (TGA)/ Differential Thermogravimetric Analysis (DTG): TGA/DTG thermograms of the control and Biofield Energy Treated berberine chloride were obtained with the help of TGA Q50TA instruments. A sample of 4-15 mg was loaded to the platinum crucible at a heating rate of 10°C/min from

25°C to 1000°C with the recent literature [46]. The % change in weight loss (W) was calculated using the following equation 5:

$$\% \text{ change in weight loss} = \frac{[W_{\text{Treated}} - W_{\text{Control}}]}{W_{\text{Control}}} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

Where W_{Control} and W_{Treated} are the weight loss of the control and Biofield Energy Treated berberine chloride, respectively.

The % change in maximum thermal degradation temperature (T_{max}) (M) was calculated using the following equation 6:

$$\% \text{ change in } T_{\text{max}} \text{ (M)} = \frac{[M_{\text{Treated}} - M_{\text{Control}}]}{M_{\text{Control}}} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

Where M_{Control} and M_{Treated} are the T_{max} values of the control and Biofield Energy Treated berberine chloride, respectively.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC): The DSC analysis of berberine chloride was performed with the help of DSC Q200, TA instruments. A sample of ~1-5 mg was loaded to the aluminium sample pan at a heating rate of 10°C/min from 30°C to 350°C [46]. The % change in melting point (T) was calculated using the following equation 7:

$$\% \text{ change in melting point} = \frac{[T_{\text{Treated}} - T_{\text{Control}}]}{T_{\text{Control}}} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

Where T_{Control} and T_{Treated} are the melting point of the control and treated samples, respectively.

The % change in the latent heat (ΔH) was calculated using the following equation 8:

$$\% \text{ change in } \Delta H = \frac{[\Delta H_{\text{Treated}} - \Delta H_{\text{Control}}]}{\Delta H_{\text{Control}}} \times 100 \quad (8)$$

Where $\Delta H_{\text{Control}}$ and $\Delta H_{\text{Treated}}$ are the latent heat of the control and treated berberine chloride, respectively.

Results and Discussion

Powder X-ray Diffraction (PXRD) Analysis

The PXRD diffractograms containing the Bragg's angle and intensity of the characteristic peaks of the control and the Biofield Energy Treated berberine chloride samples are shown in Figure 1. The further analysis of the diffractograms regarding the differences in the peak intensities and crystallite sizes of both the samples were mentioned in Table 1.

Entry No.	Bragg angle (2θ)		Intensity (cps)			Crystallite size (G, nm)		
	Control	Treated	Control	Treated	% change*	Control	Treated	% change*
1	8.93	9.12	337	240	-28.78	114	315	176.32
2	13.87	13.96	66	142	115.15	165	139	-15.76
3	14.56	14.61	84	115	36.9	252	351	39.29
4	16.17	16.3	126	159	26.19	216	215	-0.46
5	20.2	20.36	86	103	19.77	257	275	7
6	20.81	20.96	74	90	21.62	305	269	-11.8
7	24.48	24.61	349	429	22.92	141	163	15.6
8	25.3	25.53	598	621	3.85	187	224	19.79
9	26.7	26.09	455	528	16.04	29	99	241.38

*denotes the percentage change in the peak intensity and crystallite size of the Biofield Energy Treated sample with respect to the control sample

Table 1: PXRD data for the control and Biofield Energy Treated berberine chloride.

Figure 1: PXRD diffractograms of the control and Biofield Energy Treated berberine chloride.

The data indicated some major changes in the Bragg's angles of the treated sample as compared to the control sample. Moreover, the intensities of the characteristic peaks of the treated sample and the corresponding crystallite sizes also showed major alterations in comparison to the control sample. The peak intensities and crystallite sizes of the treated berberine chloride sample were observed to be significantly altered ranging from -28.78% to 115.15% and -15.76% to 241.38%, respectively, compared to the control sample. The average crystallite size of the Biofield Energy Treated sample was found as 227.78 nm, which was significantly increased by 23.05% compared the control sample (185.11 nm). The Biofield Energy Treatment has been known nowadays for its ability to alter the crystalline properties of the

compounds by changing the Bragg's angle of the characteristic peaks of the diffractograms and their corresponding peak intensities and crystallite size, which indicated the formation of a novel polymorph [47]. Hence, it is presumed that there might be the formation of a novel polymorphic form of berberine chloride with some altered characteristics in comparison to the untreated sample. Besides, such alterations in crystal habit may be useful in improving the solubility and dissolution of the compound that ultimately affects its bioavailability profile [48].

Particle Size Analysis (PSA)

The particle size analysis corresponding to d_{10} , d_{50} , d_{90} , and $D(4,3)$ for both the samples was done and results are mentioned in Table 2. The analysis indicated that the treated berberine chloride sample showed significant changes in its particle size distribution as the particle sizes at d_{10} , d_{50} , d_{90} , and $D(4,3)$ were significantly reduced by 16.89%, 34.41%, 21.88%, and 22.85%, respectively, in comparison to the control sample.

Therefore, the treated sample showed a considerable increase in its specific surface area by 14.74% that might occur due to the reduced particle size after the Biofield Energy Treatment of berberine chloride compared to the control sample. Various researchers studied the direct relationship between the particle size distribution of any drug and its performance in terms of dissolution, solubility, absorption, and bioavailability [49,50]. In addition, reducing the particle size and thereby increasing the surface area is used by various scientists in improving the bioavailability of compound [51]. Thus, it could be concluded that the treated berberine chloride might show better bioavailability after the Biofield Energy Treatment as compared to the control sample.

Parameter	d ₁₀ (µm)	d ₅₀ (µm)	d ₉₀ (µm)	D(4,3)(µm)	SSA(m ² /g)
Control	3.02	21.04	164.43	57.5	0.95
Biofield Energy Treated	2.51	13.8	128.45	44.36	1.09
Percent change* (%)	-16.89	-34.41	-21.88	-22.85	14.74

Table 2: Particle size distribution of the control and Biofield Energy Treated berberine chloride.

d₁₀, d₅₀, and d₉₀: particle diameter corresponding to 10%, 50%, and 90% of the cumulative distribution, D(4,3): the average mass-volume diameter, and SSA: the specific surface area. *denotes the percentage change in the particle size distribution of the Biofield Energy Treated sample with respect to the control sample.

Thermal Gravimetric Analysis (TGA)/ Differential Thermogravimetric Analysis (DTG)

The TGA/DTG study helps in analysing the thermal degradation pattern of the control and treated sample on heating; and the data regarding weight loss, residue, and maximum degradation temperature (T_{max}) was reported in Table 3. The scientific literature reported the thermal stability of berberine chloride up to 350 K after which the TGA curve showed four-step weight loss in the

temperature range of 350 K to 520 K [52]. The analysis of TGA thermograms (Figure 2) of the control and the treated samples reported similar data as mentioned in the literature. Besides, the TGA analysis revealed that the weight loss during thermal degradation of the treated sample was slightly increased by 3.98%, which caused 3.64% reduction in the residue weight as compared to the control sample (Table 3).

Sample	TGA		DTG			
	Total weight loss (%)	Residue %	T _{max} (°C)			
			Peak 1	Peak 2	Peak 3	Peak 4
Control	47.77	52.23	78.28	182.37	298.35	386.1
Biofield Energy Treated	49.67	50.33	83.79	185.52	302.46	397.56
% Change*	3.98	-3.64	7.04	1.73	1.38	2.97

*denotes the percentage change of the Biofield Energy Treated sample with respect to the control sample, T_{max} = the temperature at which maximum weight loss takes place in TG or peak temperature in DTG.

Table 3: TGA/DTG data of the control and Biofield Energy treated samples of berberine chloride.

Besides, the literature also reported the presence of four peaks in the DTG curve of berberine chloride that represented the various thermal decomposition products as H₂O (379K), CO (421K), CO (490K), and H₂O (514K) [52]. The DTG thermograms of the control and treated samples also revealed four peaks (Figure 3) with similar temperature as reported earlier. The comparative study of both samples indicated that the maximum thermal degradation temperature (T_{max}) corresponding to the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th Peak of the treated berberine chloride was increased by 7.04%, 1.73%, 1.38% and 2.97%, respectively compared to the control sample. Thus, the thermal analysis showed that the degradation temperature was increased in the treated sample after the Biofield Energy Treatment; thereby, indicating the improved thermal stability of the Biofield Energy Treated sample compared to the untreated sample.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) Analysis

The DSC analysis helps in studying the melting and degradation pattern of berberine chloride [53]. The analysis of thermograms of both the samples revealed the presence of six peaks in their thermograms (Figure 4). It was observed that the peak temperatures corresponding to 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th Peak of the Biofield Energy Treated sample were significantly increased by 11.03%, 1.19%, 14.96%, and 2.18%, respectively; however, it was slightly reduced by 2.03% and 0.10% for the 5th and 6th Peak, respectively compared to the control samples. The treated sample also showed significant alterations in the latent heat of fusion (ΔH) corresponding to each peak as the ΔH corresponding to 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, and 6th peak were significantly altered by 224.78%, 7.93%, 8.92%, -9.05%, -45.82%, and 10.93%, respectively, in comparison to the control sample (Table 4).

Peak	Description	Peak Temperature (°C)	ΔH (J/g)
Peak 1	Control sample	87.66	6.98
	Biofield Treated sample	97.33	22.67
	% Change*	11.03	224.78
Peak 2	Control sample	150.89	157.6
	Biofield Treated sample	152.68	170.1
	% Change*	1.19	7.93
Peak 3	Control sample	178.78	83.17
	Biofield Treated sample	205.53	90.59
	% Change*	14.96	8.92
Peak 4	Control sample	217.3	46.65
	Biofield Treated sample	222.04	42.43
	% Change*	2.18	-9.05
Peak 5	Control sample	291.31	51.51
	Biofield Treated sample	285.4	27.91
	% Change*	-2.03	-45.82
Peak 6	Control sample	315.81	169.2
	Biofield Treated sample	315.48	187.7
	% Change*	-0.1	10.93

ΔH : Latent heat of fusion; *denotes the percentage change of the Biofield Energy treated sample with respect to the control sample.

Table 4: Comparison of DSC data between the control and Biofield Energy treated berberine chloride.

Figure 4: DSC thermograms of the control and Biofield Energy treated berberine chloride.

The study indicated major changes in the melting temperature and ΔH of the 1st peak of the treated sample that was increased significantly compared with the control sample. The other data also showed the improved thermal stability of treated berberine chloride sample along with the altered latent heat that might take place because of some significant changes in the crystallization structure of the Biofield Energy Treated sample [53].

Conclusions

The Trivedi Effect®-Consciousness Energy Healing Treatment has shown a significant impact on the physicochemical properties of berberine chloride in comparison to the control sample. The PXRD peak intensities and crystallite sizes altered ranging from -28.78% to 115.15% and -15.76% to 241.38%, respectively, in comparison to the control sample. Besides, the average crystallite size of the treated sample was significantly increased by 23.05% compared to the untreated berberine chloride sample. It is suggested that such changes have taken place as the Biofield Energy Treatment might create some new polymorph of berberine chloride that could be evident from the major changes in the crystalline properties of the treated sample. The particle size data showed significant

variations in the size distribution of the berberine sample after the Biofield Energy Treatment as the particle sizes were significantly reduced by 16.89%, 34.41%, 21.88%, and 22.85%, at d10, d50, d90, and D(4,3), respectively in comparison to the control sample. The changes in the particle sizes affected the specific surface area of the treated sample, which was observed to be increased by 14.74% compared to the control sample. Such changes might attribute the significant alterations in the bioavailability profile of the treated sample by enhancing the solubility, dissolution, and absorption parameters. The TGA study revealed the increase i.e., 3.98%, in the total weight loss of the treated sample and 3.64% decrease in the residue weight of the treated berberine chloride compared to the untreated sample. However, the T_{max} corresponding to the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th peak of the treated sample was increased by 7.04%, 1.73%, 1.38%, and 2.97%, respectively compared to the untreated berberine chloride sample. The DSC data revealed that the melting point of 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th peak of the treated berberine chloride sample were increased by 11.03%, 1.19%, 14.96%, and 2.18%, respectively, compared to the control sample. The latent heat for the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, and 6th peaks of the treated sample were significantly altered by 224.78%, 7.93%, 8.92%, -9.05%, -45.82%, and 10.93%, respectively, compared to the control sample. The results indicated that the Biofield Energy Treatment might improve the degradation temperature of the treated sample that ultimately helps in improving its thermal stability as compared to the control sample. Thus, it was concluded that the Trivedi Effect®-Consciousness Energy Healing Treatment significantly affect the crystalline properties, particle sizes, surface area, and thermal stability of the berberine chloride sample. The Biofield Energy Treatment might form a new polymorph that may show better solubility, absorption, thermal stability, and bioavailability in comparison to the untreated sample. Hence, the Biofield Energy Treated sample could be used in the form of novel drug and might be used to formulate new pharmaceutical/nutraceutical products that would be more effective in the treatment of various diseases such as glaucoma, ailments related to eye and skin, diarrhea, gastric ulcers, tumor, polycystic ovary syndrome, gastroenteritis, menopausal symptoms, hypertension, high cholesterol, inflammation, malaria, hyperglycemia, congestive heart failure, arrhythmia, metabolic syndromes, thrombocytopenia, obesity, osteoporosis, liver diseases, trachoma, etc.

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